

OBSCURANTISM AT CERN ON "GOD'S PARTICLE"?

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Dear Colleagues,

The comparison of the CERN announcement of September 28, 2011 on superluminal neutrinos with the highly publicized press conference of December 12, 2011, "pre-announcing" the discovery of "God's particle" confirms what is known in informed scientific circles, namely, that there are at least two opposing factions at CERN:

A) A group of serious scientists interested in propelling scientific knowledge into the new frontiers of the 21st century that, to be "new," must be "beyond Einstein" as illustrated by superluminal neutrinos; and

B) A second group attempting to maintain 20th century lines for evident personal advantages (for non-experts, the Higgs boson is needed to maintain the validity of Einstein special relativity and the the standard model throughout the entire particle physics and related large funds). The latter group is notoriously that of "organized academic, financial and ethnic interests on Einstein" denounced by Prof. R. M. Santilli in his *Il Grande Grido* of 1984 with three volumes of documentations, which works received in 1984 a supporting review by *The Harvard Crimson* and, subsequently, numerous positive reviews in newspapers around the world <http://www.scientificethics.org/IlGrandeGrido.htm>

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In any case, no press conference "pre-announcing" a potential discovery of that magnitude is scientifically serious, particularly when considering preceding announcements by the CERN directorate that "no" evidence of the Higgs boson had emerged following the inspection of about 97% of the data. The "pre-announced" discovery should then be expected in a few events out of billions of recorded events with evident lack of scientific credibility, thus raising serious shadows of obscurantism at CERN on the Higgs boson studiously manipulated by said interests via the abuse of over one billion dollars of public European-US money.

Since the United States of America has catastrophic financial problems growing at the rate of billions dollars per day, with consequential major financial problems throughout Europe and the rest of the world, responsible citizens, observers, scholars, governmental officers and politicians should have a moment of reflection before allowing organized interests on Einstein to use additional large public funds in the current so grave financial conditions, particularly when their outcome can be an obscurantism rather than any real scientific advance.

In the scientific reality outside organized interests on Einstein, following fifty years of research on his Lie-admissible treatment of irreversible processes, the only one admitting invariance (predicting the same numerical values under the same conditions at different times), Prof. Santilli has proved beyond scientific or otherwise credible doubt that the very search for the Higgs boson has no solid scientific foundations for the following reasons (for technical details, see the references below):

1. Reversibility of Einstein's theories vz the irreversibility of scattering events During the flight in particle accelerators, protons do indeed obey Einstein's special relativity because we have in this case the sacred conditions set forth by Einstein (point particles traveling in vacuum under action-at-a-distance potential interactions). Based on these successes, during the past seventy years said interests have pushed the validity of Einstein theories also for high energy scattering process. However, special relativity is reversible over time (it characterizes the

same probability for events forward and backward in time, thus violating the causality of the real world), while the high energy inelastic scattering events at CERN are highly irreversible (their time reversal image would imply that billions of particles reconstruct the original protons and nuclei in brutal violation of causality, energy conservation and other physical laws). Therefore, any claim that Einstein's theories are "exactly" valid for irreversible scattering processes is pure academic manipulation for personal advantages. It then follows that the irreversible character of the scattering events at CERN establishes the lack of exact character of the basic discipline used for the prediction of the Higgs boson, the conventional, unitary, relativistic scattering theory, with ensuing dismissal of the very formulation of the Higgs boson as currently conjectured.

2. Inapplicability of scattering theories from the absence of "point-like wavepackets" In the 1970s, the conjecture that the hypothetical quarks are physical particles in our spacetime (even though they cannot even be defined in it!!) was pushed by said interests because point-like constituents of particles are necessary to maintain the validity of Einstein's special relativity within the hyperdense medium inside hadrons. This political posture was pushed despite numerous opposing technical arguments published in serious refereed journals (all studiously ignored via the abuse of academic credibility and very large public funds). These opposing arguments were voiced by Gell-Mann, Santilli, Barut and other qualified scientists who proved that classification models cannot allow the characterization of the structure, as it was historically the case for the atoms (that required one model for the classification into families and a "different" yet compatible model for the structure of each element of a given family). However, as Santilli stresses in his works, "there are no point-like wavepackets in nature." Consequently, despite the hypothetical point-like character of the hypothetical quarks, the scattering regions at the high energy currently reached at CERN is immensely far from being a bunch of isolated points (as needed by said interests to maintain Einsteinian theories), and it is instead by one of the densest regions detected by mankind to date, characterized by the total mutual immersion of wavepackets and charge distributions of a large number of particles in

a small region of space. Under these conditions, we have the unavoidable emergence of contact, variationally nonselfadjoint, therefore non-Hamiltonian, therefore non-unitary interactions. In turn, this occurrence (as well as the irreversibility of the process) mandates the need for a non-unitary covering of the conventional, unitary relativistic scattering theory fully available for some time yet ignored at CERN. But non-unitary theories are known to violate causality and other laws, thus leaving Santilli non-unitary/geno-unitary Lie-admissible formulations as the only credible scientific choice.

3. Lack of meaning of the Higgs mass due to nonunitary irreversible effects The current conjecture (based on the political assumption of the "exact" validity of Einstein's theories inside the scattering region) is that the Higgs boson has the mass of 115-130 GeV/c². This conjecture has scientific sense solely when the boson is isolated in vacuum according to Einstein's sacred conditions. But in reality, the Higgs boson is conjectured as mediating processes within the hyperdense scattering region in a very small region of space under which conditions we have inevitable non-Hamiltonian/non-unitary interactions. Prof. Santilli proved in 1978, when he was at Harvard University (for which reason said interests at Harvard opposed his studies there - see Il Grande Grido), that irreversible non-unitary interactions cause a new renormalization (he called "mutation") of the intrinsic characteristics of particles, beginning with a large mutation of the mass, of course, solely occurring in interior conditions. Consequently, the very conjecture of 115-130 GeV/c² as the Higgs mass has no solid scientific value. In actuality, when we reach the density of the scattering region of the ongoing experiments at CERN, the old Feynman ideas of interactions mediated by particle exchanges (which is unquestionably valid for the conditions of the original formulations, electromagnetic interactions), after being pushed to apply for all; scattering by organized academic, financial and ethnic interests on Einstein via the abuse of large public funds and academic credibility, said Feynman's idea loses its validity for very high energy scattering events at CERN in favor of new vistas in providing a more accurate, thus irreversible, representation of high energy scattering without any prediction of any new particle.

For technical treatments, serious scholars should study the recent five papers available below in free pdf download.

Yours truly,

REFERENCES "Nonunitary Lie-isotopic and Lie-admissible scattering theories of hadronic mechanics" R. M. Santilli and A. O. E. Animalu, Papers I, II, III, IV and V, in the Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Lie-Admissible Treatments of Irreversible Processes, C. Corda, Editor, Kathmandu University (2011)

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